

Supplementary information

**Power Factor Improvement in a Hybrid Solid-Liquid Thermoelectric Device
Formed by Sb:SnO₂ in Contact with a Chromium Complex Solution**

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Fig. S1. (a-c) Open-circuit voltage vs temperature difference and (d-f) current-voltage plots for the systems 1-Cr to 3-Cr. Results with and without the presence of the 0.1 M $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ in 3-MPN electrolyte are shown.

Fig. S2. (a-c) Open-circuit voltage vs temperature difference and (d-f) current-voltage plots for the systems 1-3MPN to 3-3MPN. Results with and without the presence of the 3-MPN solvent acting as electrolyte are shown.

Fig. S3. ^1H NMR spectra in CD_3CN of the 3-methoxypropionitrile (3-MPN) (blue) and the 0.1M solution of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ in 3-MPN (red). (a) Overlapped spectra and (b) comparison with magnification. 3-Methoxypropionitrile (3-MPN): ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 3.54 (t, $J=6.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.34 (s, 3H), 2.61 (t, $J=6.0$ Hz, 2H).

Fig. S4. Seebeck coefficient and electrical resistance as a function of temperature for an Sb:SnO₂ film.

Fig. S5. Impedance spectroscopy spectra under $\Delta T=5$ K of the Sb:SnO₂ films from **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..** (a-c) Films 1-Cr to 3-Cr, without and with the presence of the 0.1 M Cr(acac)₃ solution in 3-MPN. (d-f) Films 1-3MPN to 3-3MPN, without and with the

presence of only 3-MPN. The temperatures indicated in each case are the cold side temperatures. The inset in (a) is the equivalent circuit used.